

COVER SHEET FOR PROPOSAL TO THE NATIONAL SCIENCE FOUNDATION

PROGRAM ANNOUNCEMENT/SOLICITATION NO./CLOSING DATE/if not in response to a program announcement/solicitation enter NSF 14-1					FOR NSF USE ONLY			
NSF 11-547			02/13/14		NSF PROPOSAL NUMBER			
FOR CONSIDERATION BY NSF ORGANIZATION UNIT(S) (Indicate the most specific unit known, i.e. program, division, etc.)								
BCS - ARCHAEOLOGY								
DATE RECEIVED	NUMBER OF COPIES	DIVISION ASSIGNED	FUND CODE	DUNS# (Data Universal Numbering System)	FILE LOCATION			
				073133571				
EMPLOYER IDENTIFICATION NUMBER (EIN) OR TAXPAYER IDENTIFICATION NUMBER (TIN)		SHOW PREVIOUS AWARD NO. IF THIS IS <input type="checkbox"/> A RENEWAL <input type="checkbox"/> AN ACCOMPLISHMENT-BASED RENEWAL		IS THIS PROPOSAL BEING SUBMITTED TO ANOTHER FEDERAL AGENCY? YES <input type="checkbox"/> NO <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> IF YES, LIST ACRONYM(S)				
386006309								
NAME OF ORGANIZATION TO WHICH AWARD SHOULD BE MADE			ADDRESS OF AWARDEE ORGANIZATION, INCLUDING 9 DIGIT ZIP CODE					
University of Michigan Ann Arbor			Room 1062					
AWARDEE ORGANIZATION CODE (IF KNOWN)			Ann Arbor, MI 481091274					
0023259000			US					
NAME OF PRIMARY PLACE OF PERF			ADDRESS OF PRIMARY PLACE OF PERF, INCLUDING 9 DIGIT ZIP CODE					
University of Michigan Ann Arbor			University of Michigan Ann Arbor					
			SP.					
IS AWARDEE ORGANIZATION (Check All That Apply) (See GPG II.C For Definitions)								
		<input type="checkbox"/> SMALL BUSINESS		<input type="checkbox"/> MINORITY BUSINESS		<input type="checkbox"/> IF THIS IS A PRELIMINARY PROPOSAL THEN CHECK HERE		
		<input type="checkbox"/> FOR-PROFIT ORGANIZATION		<input type="checkbox"/> WOMAN-OWNED BUSINESS				
TITLE OF PROPOSED PROJECT Doctoral Dissertation Improvement Grant : Social Organization and Mortuary Practices at Marroquies Bajos, Jaen, Spain								
REQUESTED AMOUNT		PROPOSED DURATION (1-60 MONTHS)		REQUESTED STARTING DATE		SHOW RELATED PRELIMINARY PROPOSAL NO. IF APPLICABLE		
\$ 25,180		12 months		05/15/14				
THIS PROPOSAL INCLUDES ANY OF THE ITEMS LISTED BELOW								
<input type="checkbox"/> BEGINNING INVESTIGATOR (GPG I.G.2)			<input type="checkbox"/> HUMAN SUBJECTS (GPG II.D.7) Human Subjects Assurance Number _____					
<input type="checkbox"/> DISCLOSURE OF LOBBYING ACTIVITIES (GPG II.C.1.e)			Exemption Subsection _____ or IRB App. Date _____					
<input type="checkbox"/> PROPRIETARY & PRIVILEGED INFORMATION (GPG I.D, II.C.1.d)			<input type="checkbox"/> INTERNATIONAL ACTIVITIES: COUNTRY/COUNTRIES INVOLVED (GPG II.C.2.j)					
<input type="checkbox"/> HISTORIC PLACES (GPG II.C.2.j)								
<input type="checkbox"/> VERTEBRATE ANIMALS (GPG II.D.6) IACUC App. Date _____								
PHS Animal Welfare Assurance Number _____			<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> COLLABORATIVE STATUS					
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> FUNDING MECHANISM Research - other than RAPID or EAGER			Not a collaborative proposal					
PI/PD DEPARTMENT			PI/PD POSTAL ADDRESS					
Anthropology			3003 South State St.					
PI/PD FAX NUMBER			Room 1062					
734-763-7783			Ann Arbor, MI 481091271					
			United States					
NAMES (TYPED)		High Degree	Yr of Degree	Telephone Number	Email Address			
Robin Beck		MPhil	2004	734-764-1817	rabeck@umich.edu			
Jessica Beck		MA	2011	734-763-6438	jessbeck@umich.edu			
CO-PI/PD								
CO-PI/PD								
CO-PI/PD								

CERTIFICATION PAGE

Certification for Authorized Organizational Representative (or Equivalent) or Individual Applicant

By electronically signing and submitting this proposal, the Authorized Organizational Representative (AOR) or Individual Applicant is: (1) certifying that statements made herein are true and complete to the best of his/her knowledge; and (2) agreeing to accept the obligation to comply with NSF award terms and conditions if an award is made as a result of this application. Further, the applicant is hereby providing certifications regarding conflict of interest (when applicable), drug-free workplace, debarment and suspension, lobbying activities (see below), nondiscrimination, flood hazard insurance (when applicable), responsible conduct of research, organizational support, Federal tax obligations, unpaid Federal tax liability, and criminal convictions as set forth in the NSF Proposal & Award Policies & Procedures Guide, Part I: the Grant Proposal Guide (GPG). Willful provision of false information in this application and its supporting documents or in reports required under an ensuing award is a criminal offense (U.S. Code, Title 18, Section 1001).

Certification Regarding Conflict of Interest

The AOR is required to complete certifications stating that the organization has implemented and is enforcing a written policy on conflicts of interest (COI), consistent with the provisions of AAG Chapter IV.A.; that, to the best of his/her knowledge, all financial disclosures required by the conflict of interest policy were made; and that conflicts of interest, if any, were, or prior to the organization's expenditure of any funds under the award, will be, satisfactorily managed, reduced or eliminated in accordance with the organization's conflict of interest policy. Conflicts that cannot be satisfactorily managed, reduced or eliminated and research that proceeds without the imposition of conditions or restrictions when a conflict of interest exists, must be disclosed to NSF via use of the Notifications and Requests Module in FastLane.

Drug Free Work Place Certification

By electronically signing the Certification Pages, the Authorized Organizational Representative (or equivalent), is providing the Drug Free Work Place Certification contained in Exhibit II-3 of the Grant Proposal Guide.

Debarment and Suspension Certification

(If answer "yes", please provide explanation.)

Is the organization or its principals presently debarred, suspended, proposed for debarment, declared ineligible, or voluntarily excluded from covered transactions by any Federal department or agency?

Yes

No

By electronically signing the Certification Pages, the Authorized Organizational Representative (or equivalent) or Individual Applicant is providing the Debarment and Suspension Certification contained in Exhibit II-4 of the Grant Proposal Guide.

Certification Regarding Lobbying

This certification is required for an award of a Federal contract, grant, or cooperative agreement exceeding \$100,000 and for an award of a Federal loan or a commitment providing for the United States to insure or guarantee a loan exceeding \$150,000.

Certification for Contracts, Grants, Loans and Cooperative Agreements

The undersigned certifies, to the best of his or her knowledge and belief, that:

- (1) No Federal appropriated funds have been paid or will be paid, by or on behalf of the undersigned, to any person for influencing or attempting to influence an officer or employee of any agency, a Member of Congress, an officer or employee of Congress, or an employee of a Member of Congress in connection with the awarding of any Federal contract, the making of any Federal grant, the making of any Federal loan, the entering into of any cooperative agreement, and the extension, continuation, renewal, amendment, or modification of any Federal contract, grant, loan, or cooperative agreement.
- (2) If any funds other than Federal appropriated funds have been paid or will be paid to any person for influencing or attempting to influence an officer or employee of any agency, a Member of Congress, an officer or employee of Congress, or an employee of a Member of Congress in connection with this Federal contract, grant, loan, or cooperative agreement, the undersigned shall complete and submit Standard Form-LLL, "Disclosure of Lobbying Activities," in accordance with its instructions.
- (3) The undersigned shall require that the language of this certification be included in the award documents for all subawards at all tiers including subcontracts, subgrants, and contracts under grants, loans, and cooperative agreements and that all subrecipients shall certify and disclose accordingly.

This certification is a material representation of fact upon which reliance was placed when this transaction was made or entered into. Submission of this certification is a prerequisite for making or entering into this transaction imposed by section 1352, Title 31, U.S. Code. Any person who fails to file the required certification shall be subject to a civil penalty of not less than \$10,000 and not more than \$100,000 for each such failure.

Certification Regarding Nondiscrimination

By electronically signing the Certification Pages, the Authorized Organizational Representative (or equivalent) is providing the Certification Regarding Nondiscrimination contained in Exhibit II-6 of the Grant Proposal Guide.

Certification Regarding Flood Hazard Insurance

Two sections of the National Flood Insurance Act of 1968 (42 USC §4012a and §4106) bar Federal agencies from giving financial assistance for acquisition or construction purposes in any area identified by the Federal Emergency Management Agency (FEMA) as having special flood hazards unless the:

- (1) community in which that area is located participates in the national flood insurance program; and
- (2) building (and any related equipment) is covered by adequate flood insurance.

By electronically signing the Certification Pages, the Authorized Organizational Representative (or equivalent) or Individual Applicant located in FEMA-designated special flood hazard areas is certifying that adequate flood insurance has been or will be obtained in the following situations:

- (1) for NSF grants for the construction of a building or facility, regardless of the dollar amount of the grant; and
- (2) for other NSF grants when more than \$25,000 has been budgeted in the proposal for repair, alteration or improvement (construction) of a building or facility.

Certification Regarding Responsible Conduct of Research (RCR)

(This certification is not applicable to proposals for conferences, symposia, and workshops.)

By electronically signing the Certification Pages, the Authorized Organizational Representative is certifying that, in accordance with the NSF Proposal & Award Policies & Procedures Guide, Part II, Award & Administration Guide (AAG) Chapter IV.B., the institution has a plan in place to provide appropriate training and oversight in the responsible and ethical conduct of research to undergraduates, graduate students and postdoctoral researchers who will be supported by NSF to conduct research. The AOR shall require that the language of this certification be included in any award documents for all subawards at all tiers.

CERTIFICATION PAGE - CONTINUED

Certification Regarding Organizational Support

By electronically signing the Certification Pages, the Authorized Organizational Representative (or equivalent) is certifying that there is organizational support for the proposal as required by Section 526 of the America COMPETES Reauthorization Act of 2010. This support extends to the portion of the proposal developed to satisfy the Broader Impacts Review Criterion as well as the Intellectual Merit Review Criterion, and any additional review criteria specified in the solicitation. Organizational support will be made available, as described in the proposal, in order to address the broader impacts and intellectual merit activities to be undertaken.

Certification Regarding Federal Tax Obligations

When the proposal exceeds \$5,000,000, the Authorized Organizational Representative (or equivalent) is required to complete the following certification regarding Federal tax obligations. By electronically signing the Certification pages, the Authorized Organizational Representative is certifying that, to the best of their knowledge and belief, the proposing organization:

- (1) has filed all Federal tax returns required during the three years preceding this certification;
- (2) has not been convicted of a criminal offense under the Internal Revenue Code of 1986; and
- (3) has not, more than 90 days prior to this certification, been notified of any unpaid Federal tax assessment for which the liability remains unsatisfied, unless the assessment is the subject of an installment agreement or offer in compromise that has been approved by the Internal Revenue Service and is not in default, or the assessment is the subject of a non-frivolous administrative or judicial proceeding.

Certification Regarding Unpaid Federal Tax Liability

When the proposing organization is a corporation, the Authorized Organizational Representative (or equivalent) is required to complete the following certification regarding Federal Tax Liability:

By electronically signing the Certification Pages, the Authorized Organizational Representative (or equivalent) is certifying that the corporation has no unpaid Federal tax liability that has been assessed, for which all judicial and administrative remedies have been exhausted or lapsed, and that is not being paid in a timely manner pursuant to an agreement with the authority responsible for collecting the tax liability.

Certification Regarding Criminal Convictions

When the proposing organization is a corporation, the Authorized Organizational Representative (or equivalent) is required to complete the following certification regarding Criminal Convictions:

By electronically signing the Certification Pages, the Authorized Organizational Representative (or equivalent) is certifying that the corporation has not been convicted of a felony criminal violation under any Federal law within the 24 months preceding the date on which the certification is signed.

AUTHORIZED ORGANIZATIONAL REPRESENTATIVE		SIGNATURE		DATE	
NAME					
TELEPHONE NUMBER	EMAIL ADDRESS			FAX NUMBER	

Overview

The Iberian Copper Age is a period dominated by the emergence of early complex societies. In sharp contrast with the preceding Neolithic, the Chalcolithic is characterized by agricultural intensification, population aggregation, political centralization and the appearance of ‘mega-villages’ on the landscape. Previous research has focused on the phenomenon of collective burial to suggest that these broad-scale social processes are underwritten by a ‘communally-organized society’. However the internal organization of such communities is still poorly understood, particularly because the taphonomy and social function of such collective burials are underexplored. At 113 ha in size, Marroquíes Bajos is one of the largest settlements known for the time period, and contains evidence of four different burial programs. This project’s bioarchaeological analysis of the mortuary variability at the site will allow for the investigation of whether Iberian Copper Age societies were collectively organized, or whether significant disparities in health, diet or material culture existed among the social units being represented in these burials. Through osteological analysis, isotopic analysis of diet, AMS radiocarbon dating, and an archaeological analysis of tomb form and grave goods, my investigation at Marroquíes Bajos will allow for a more nuanced reconstruction of the ways in which Copper Age societies were organized, while deepening our understanding of how and why collective burials were used by prehistoric populations.

Intellectual Merit

This research will contribute to a growing body of work on the significance of collective burials in prehistory. While this topic that has merited increasing anthropological attention in recent years, few Iberian-specific analyses have been conducted that permit us to understand what such large-scale sites represent in terms of social organization. Importantly, a better understanding of the communal interments so characteristic of the Iberian Chalcolithic will allow for a more detailed understanding of how these amorphously ‘collective’ early complex societies were actually organized. This project’s intellectual merit lies in the fact that its multi-component bioarchaeological and archaeological analysis offers a novel approach to mortuary work in Spain, and should offer a framework for future projects.

Broader Impacts

The broader impacts of this project are two-fold. First, my project involves the analysis of salvage-excavated materials that would otherwise sit untouched in museum storage. The professional expansion of Spanish archaeology during the 1970s and the impressive increase in survey and excavation during the 1980s and 1990s has not been matched by an equivalent degree of analysis of recovered cultural materials. Secondly, human remains are a unique type of cultural evidence that merit timely cleaning, analysis, storage and display. By analyzing unstudied, salvage-excavated collections, my project aids in the development of synthetic models of late prehistory in Iberia, and its bioarchaeological focus ensures that the remains of these Copper Age individuals will be used to make a significant contribution to our understanding of the human past. I will disseminate my results to the academic community in presentations at national and international conferences in multiple fields, publication in peer-reviewed journals, and ultimately a book detailing the ways that the mortuary record of Marroquíes Bajos illustrates the development of social complexity in Iberia.

PROJECT DESCRIPTION

The Iberian Copper Age (c. 3,100-2200 B.C.) was characterized by agricultural intensification, population aggregation, and political centralization - broad-scale social processes that still structure contemporary human communities. Understanding how such early complex societies emerge, and identifying the strategies that averted or accelerated their collapse, is key to understanding the evolution of human social complexity more generally. In particular, it is important to isolate the degree to which the emergent logistical complexity of such societies necessarily entails social inequality, in terms of access to subsistence or social resources. By investigating how Iberian Copper Age mortuary practices were used to either hide or highlight the social inequalities that occurred in tandem with the broad-scale social processes that defined prehistoric Europe in the third millennium, I will contribute to a broader anthropological understanding of the intricate relationship between inequality and the rise of early social complexity.

The southern Iberian Chalcolithic was a period in which large-scale, fortified settlements became central places that attracted relatively large regional populations (Díaz-del-Río 2013). While the emergence of large Copper Age centers is well-documented, the internal organization and social strategies that facilitated the concentration and control of local populations at such centers for almost a millennium are still poorly understood (Díaz-del-Río 2004b). The nature of Copper Age funerary practices is particularly problematic— because individuals were buried collectively (Mathers 1984a); it is difficult to distinguish individual social roles, or hypothesize about the nature of Chalcolithic social organization.

My dissertation research at the Copper Age settlement of Marroquíes Bajos – the second largest ditched and walled enclosure in Iberia – is well suited to unpacking the relationship between the “undifferentiated funerary ideologies” of the Chalcolithic (García Sanjuán and Díaz-del-Río, 2006), and the contrasting archaeological evidence for social hierarchy that suggests social rank and inequality. I propose to investigate whether funerary variability at Marroquíes Bajos reflects (i) a multi-stage mortuary program; (ii) the use of different mortuary programs by different social groups or (iii) diachronic change in mortuary practices. Differentiating between these models will illuminate whether Copper Age society was collectively organized, or whether significant disparities in health, diet or material culture exist among the social units being represented in these burials.

At Marroquíes Bajos, I will undertake a bioarchaeological analysis of five of the seven mortuary locales at the site, comparing them to the two mortuary areas that have been analyzed (Sánchez et al., 2005, Cámara et al., 2010). These unstudied mortuary areas encompass four distinct burial programs and represent over one hundred individuals. An analysis of these mortuary populations will allow for an examination of the ways in which mortuary treatment and bioarchaeological characteristics (like MNI, categorical age, sex, disease-experience, trauma, and diet), evolve relative to the development and decline of the site itself. Understanding mortuary variability at such large-scale Iberian centers will allow for a more nuanced reconstruction of the ways in which Copper Age societies were organized, while deepening our understanding of how and why collective burials were used by prehistoric populations.

MORTUARY PRACTICES AND SOCIAL ORGANIZATION

Theoretical constructions of the relationship between mortuary practices and social structure are rooted in early work that explored funerary ritual as a ‘trait’ within a broader cultural and historical framework, (Kroeber 1927; Childe 1945). This research was augmented by processual investigations of explicit relationships between social organization and mortuary practices in human societies (Binford 1971; Saxe 1970; Brown 1971; Brown 1995), particularly the correspondence between the social identities assumed by a living individual and their subsequent mortuary treatment (Saxe 1970). Such research explored the patterning of variables like spatial organization (Renfrew 1973; Goldstein 1981; Chapman 1995), social rank (Brown 1971; Tainter 1975; Peebles & Kus

1977) and energy expenditure (Tainter 1978) to reconstruct aspects of the social organization of prehistoric communities.

Importantly, however, such work has been tempered by ethnographic explorations that underscore the ways that funerary practices can be used to manipulate and blur social distinctions maintained in life (Bloch 1968; Ucko 1969; Parker-Pearson 2005). However, changes in funerary practices do not only reflect shifts in social organization and ideology. Ethnographic evidence suggests that mortuary rituals are also affected by factors like local environmental change, technology and fashion (Kroeber 1927; Metcalf, 1981; Parker Pearson 1982; Hijaya 1983; Palgi and Abramovitch 1984; Cannon et al., 1989; Rainville 1989). Despite these multiple influences on mortuary ritual, an important thread tying diverse funerary practices together is that they reflect an identity ascribed to the deceased by living members of a social group – as Lillios underscores, “the dead don’t bury the dead, the living do” (1999: 241). Cross-culturally, living communities isolate and identify particular social identities (Goodenough 1965) that are referenced during mortuary ritual (O’Shea 1984). While not all aspects of such differentiation are preserved in the archaeological record (Beckett and Robb 2006), all evidence suggests that there are regularities in mortuary differentiation, individual social roles, and social complexity that “link...aspects of the living society and its procedure for the disposal of the dead” (O’Shea 1984: 21).

Most archaeological research connecting mortuary practices and social organization has focused on individual burials, where it is understood that a relatively direct relationship exists between grave form, grave goods, and the social identity of the interred individual. Such an approach is apparent in archaeological investigations of Iberian Bronze Age societies, when individuals were buried under household floors with distinctive grave goods (Mathers 1984; Lull 2000; Lull et al., 2005; García Sanjuán 2006). In contrast, societies practicing collective burials are viewed as promoting communal identities at the expense of individual identities, as “the social collectivity is represented physically by thorough-going commingling of human bone and skeletal parts” and “the integrity of the individual is lost upon death” (Brown 1995:5). This conclusion is particularly prominent in studies of prehistoric social organization in Europe. Rather than identifying and interpreting the explicit relationships between formal, taphonomic, and bioarchaeological components of collective burials, previous research on collective burials focused on social meaning (Chapman 1981). As Lull underscores, the underlying assumption is that membership in such an inhumation was a signal of social identity, as “in death [these individuals] returned to the unit that gave them social significance” (2000:585). However, despite initial informative analyses of intrasite mortuary variability (Chapman 1981) and discussions of Copper Age social organization (Chapman 1977, 1990, 2003; Díaz-del-Río 2006; García Sanjuán 2006), we still do not know how these social units were organized or delineated, or whether these collective burials conceal a significant degree of social inequality. Instead, European collective burials tend to be treated as instances of amorphous ancestor cults (García Sanjuán 2006; Waterman and Thomas 2010), an interpretative crutch that has become so in vogue that some archaeologists have bemoaned that there are simply “too many ancestors” populating the literature (Whitley 2002).

Comparatively the mass investments of communal labor and collective burial practices are geographically and chronologically widely spread from Chalcolithic Europe to Initial Horizon Peru to the Hopewell communities of the American Midwest. However, before making broad-scale interpretations, we must understand the social processes that produce these mortuary records (Roksandic 2002). Specifically, we must question **(1) how such collective inhumations were produced by living groups; (2) what factors structure and influence the mortuary variability inherent in the archaeological record and (3) whether similar forms of mortuary treatment reflect or conceal significant differences in lived experience in prehistory.**

LATE PREHISTORIC SOUTHERN IBERIA

Contemporary southern Iberia is well known for its heat and aridity when compared to the rest of Europe. Though long-term anthropogenic environmental degradation has exacerbated this climate extreme, portions of the Iberian southeast have been argued to be hot and dry in prehistory, with unpredictable rainfall of less than 300 mm annually (Chapman 1978; 2008; Mathers 1984a; Gilman 2001), though the most recent paleoenvironmental research suggests that while rainfall levels were similar to the present, the greater amounts of vegetation cover in prehistory actually made the region wetter and more verdant during the third millennium (Molina and Cámara 2005). In contrast to contemporary Almería, the Guadalquivir Basin is less arid, and likely has the highest agropastoral potential in all Iberia. Diverse environmental conditions range from the river basin dotted with permanent springs to the northern mountains of the Sierra Morena and the gentle hill relief of the southern *campiña*. Here, rainfall ranges from 300-1600mm annually depending on micro-environment (Chapman 2008; Díaz-del-Río 2004b).

Chalcolithic inhabitants of the region pursued a subsistence strategy of ‘mixed farming’, combining dry and some irrigated farming with pastoralism, hunting and gathering (Mathers 1984a; Micó Perez 1995; Vicent García 1995). Paleobotanical evidence documents cultivation of wheat, barley, linseed, beans and peas, while zooarchaeological remains reveal the husbandry of pigs, cattle and sheep/goats (Chapman 1978). This agropastoral package changed little regardless of environmental aridity (Gilman 1987). As in other areas of Europe, such animal domesticates were not solely exploited for their meat, but were also used for such ‘secondary products’ as milk, transport and traction (Sherratt 1983; Harrison 1985).

While the Late Neolithic record is scarce for Iberia (Díaz-Andreu 1995; Forenbaheer 1999; Gilman 2001), agricultural production was intensified with the advent of the Copper Age. One of the most marked changes at the turn of the third millennium is the appearance of large-scale, permanent, and often fortified settlements, which occur in tandem with increasing evidence for craft specialization, metallurgical production, megalithic funerary monuments, the development of wealth differentials in grave goods, the long-distance procurement of exotic materials and the circulation of luxury goods (Chapman 1990, 2003, 2008; García-Sanjuán and Murillo-Barroso 2013; García Sanjuán et al., 2013; Gilman 1987, 2001; Nocete 2005; Schumacher 2012; Vicent García 1995). Such hallmarks of developing social and economic complexity have been well investigated in southeast Spain and the southwestern realm of the Portuguese Estremadura (Gilman 1987), but similar signatures of complexity exist in the lower Duero basin (Díaz-Andreu 1995), the Central Meseta (Díaz-del-Río 2004a; 2006; Delibes de Castro et al., 1994) and Portugal more generally (Forenbaheer 1999).

Various factors have been suggested to trigger the aggregation of populations and increase in social-complexity during the third millennium B.C. These include the development of systems of irrigation and water control (Chapman 1978; Gilman and Thornes 1985), the concentration of agricultural surplus in a system of staple finance (Díaz-Andreu 1995; Gilman 1987), the conversion of surplus into valuables or exotic products of long-distance trade (Díaz-Andreu 1995; Gilman 1987), the increasingly intense cultivation of cereals and livestock (Mathers 1984a), the exploitation of domesticates for their secondary products (Sherratt 1983; Harrison 1985; Vicent García 1995) and the production and incorporation of new metallurgical products and luxury goods into systems of exchange controlled by elites (Nocete et al., 2005, 2008, 2010). Whatever the catalyst for complexity, it is widely agreed that the Chalcolithic system undergoes a radical reorganization during the period 2400-2200 BCE, with the decline or abandonment of sites that had previously been centers of activity, fissioning of populations, and a general collapse of inter-settlement organization (Díaz-del-Río 2004a, 2004b; García Sanjuán and Murillo-Barroso 2013; Nocete et al. 2010).

Mortuary Practices in Copper Age Iberia

Iberian mortuary practices during Late Prehistory undergo a key transformation from communal deposits in pits, natural and artificial caves, and megalithic chambered tombs, to inhumations that were structurally simpler, but emphasized individual identity through the use of more elaborate grave goods and spatial segregation (Díaz-del-Río 2006; Forenbaier 1999; Gilman 2001; Mathers 1984a, 1984b;). During the Neolithic and Copper Age, individuals of all genders and ages were buried communally in artificial caves or rock shelters with ‘utilitarian’ grave goods of pottery or stone tools, a tradition that was elaborated over time through the use of megalithic tombs that required community labor for construction (Díaz-del-Río 2006; Garcia Sanjuán 2006). Importantly, regional variability emerged in tomb forms during the Chalcolithic, with segmented tombs and wealth differentials in grave goods occurring more commonly in Almería, an arid region where the control of irrigation systems may have helped elites maintain their authority (Gilman 2001; Mathers 1984a). During the Bronze Age, the incorporation of greater numbers of luxury and symbolic goods into specific graves and the increased number of child burials attest to the growing emphasis on social inequality and the identity of *individuals*, rather than sodalities or lineages (Lull 2000; Mathers 1984a). This later period witnesses the rise of subfloor household burials, a trend believed to signify the growing importance of the nuclear family at the expense of the clan or extended family (Lull 2000; Lull et al., 2005; Garcia Sanjuán 2006). The gradual replacement of large-scale communal tombs by individual containers or small pit burials also suggests a decreased amount of community investment in mortuary practices, while the standardization of grave goods and tomb form is indicative of the existence of widely recognized symbolic framework with which to signal social differentiation (Mathers 1984b; Sanjuán 2006).

Copper Age Marroquies Bajos

At 113 hectares, Marroquies Bajos is one of the largest sites known for the Iberian Copper Age. The settlement is characterized by five concentric ditches and an adobe wall surrounding the fourth ditch, with a postulated spatial division between the residential component of the site and outlying storage and fields (Zafra de la Torre et al., 1999). To date, the overarching chronology for Marroquies Bajos based on dates from archaeological features suggests an initial foundation of the settlement in the first half of the third millennium, substantial investments of communal labor in the multiple ditch and wall system starting circa 2450 B.C., and a dramatic decrease in human activity at around 2,000 B.C. A gradual shift in domestic architecture was from functionally differentiated dwellings grouped around central plazas after 2450 cal BC to multiple domestic complexes bordered by stone walls after 2200 cal BC (Cámara et al., 2012, 2013; Díaz-del-Río 2004b; Zafra de la Torre et al., 1999). Though regional archaeologists have distinguished between necropolises (N) and *fosas comunes*, or mass graves (F), salvage excavations suggest at least four spatially segregated mortuary tracks: commingled inhumations in discrete structures at N2 (Pérez Martínez 2005), large collective deposits in pits lacking discrete structures, as at F1, F2 and F3 (Sánchez et al., 2005; Crespo Kayser et al. 2009), multiple individual inhumations in discrete structures at N1 and N3 (Serrano Peña 2000; Garcia Cuevas 2005; Garcia Cuevas et al., 2012; Cámara Serrano et al., 2013), and finally the burial of a number of individuals in the artificial caves of N4, also known as Marroquies Altos (Espantaléon Jubes 1957, 1960; de Pellicer 1968; Manzano and Martínez 2005) (**Figure 1**). F1 has been dated to the second half of the third millennium (Sánchez et al., 2005) and the remains of contained four adult males and one subadult individual. The mortuary population of N3 was much larger, with over 204 individuals of both sexes and all age categories present. Most of the mortuary structures in this necropolis appeared to cluster between 2531-2132 cal BC (Cámara et al., 2010: 84).

RESEARCH QUESTIONS AND EXPECTATIONS

Iberianist archaeologists broadly agree that evidence from settlement patterns, domestic organization, subsistence practices, craft production and funerary ritual indicates that Copper Age communities were organized along collective lines (Díaz-del-Río 2004a, 2004b; García Sanjuán and Díaz-del-Río 2006; Gilman 2013) rather than the hierarchical and inegalitarian form of organization that characterizes states (but see Nocete et al., 2006, 2008, 2010). Copper Age communities have been described variously as “pre-state societies organized along communal economic principles” (Díaz-del-Río and García Sanjuán 2006), “segmentary groups” (Díaz-del-Río 2006) and ‘lineage-based’ communal institutions (Mathers 1984; Gilman 2001). However, the *nature* of this collective organization remains amorphous, and the degree to which collective mortuary practices either mirror or mask nascent social inequality is unclear. Was labor organized by nuclear families, regulated by differentially ranked kin groups or lineages, or were incipient chiefs or ‘big men’ (Chapman 2008; Díaz-del-Río 2004b) responsible for marshaling and maintaining large-scale investments of labor?

Until we answer basic questions about the nature of Copper Age mortuary variability, it is impossible to rigorously analyze the amorphously ‘collective’ form of social organization that has been argued to underlie the explosion of complexity in third millennium Iberia. My dissertation research evaluates the nature of the mortuary variability at Marroquíes Bajos. I will specifically evaluate three models:

Model 1: Multiple funerary programs were pursued simultaneously, with members of different social groups buried in different locales.

Model 2: Different mortuary areas represent sequential components of the same funerary program, where the archaeological record has simply captured individual bodies undergoing different stages of the same process.

Model 3: Different mortuary areas reflect diachronic change in funerary ritual at the site.

These models are not mutually exclusive, but the strength of each signature has important implications for understanding how Copper Age groups handled the multiple pressures associated with increasing social complexity. If different burial areas were used by different social groups, bioarchaeological analysis will reveal the kinds of social distinctions that were necessary to manage and maintain large-scale communal labor projects. If the burial areas represent a multi-stage mortuary program, only select individuals will have received more costly secondary processing, contributing to our understanding of the degree of social ranking present during the Copper Age. Finally, if mortuary variability is the result of chronological change, it will clarify how funerary practices evolve relative to the origin, maintenance and collapse of early complex centers. Evaluating the complexity and organization of the funerary program at this ‘matrix village’ will provide an enhanced understanding of the complexity and organization of Copper Age Iberian societies.

To evaluate these models, I will focus on three evidentiary domains, each of which seeks to answer a specific set of research questions: (1) bioarchaeological characteristics of the mortuary population; (2) material culture and (3) stable isotope analysis and radiocarbon dating. I will use these domains to test three specific models of funerary practices, (outlined in **Figure 3**), and analyze whether variability in mortuary practices at such large-scale sites is predominantly chronological, is related to contemporaneous multi-stage mortuary programs, or is rooted in distinctions between social groups. Understanding *how* the mortuary record of Marroquíes Bajos was produced will make it possible to address whether complex Copper Age societies were truly organized collectively, or whether there are formal and bioarchaeological signatures of inequality within and between social units.

Domain 1: Bioarchaeological Analysis

- Do anatomical completeness and representation differ between the mortuary locales?
- Do signatures of multi-stage mortuary tracks differ between mortuary locales?
- Are there significant differences in the demographic composition of each mortuary locale in terms of age, sex or paleopathology?

Collecting data on skeletal completion, articulation, indications of primary processing like cutmarks or gnawmarks, and the orientation of elements within formal disposal areas allows researchers to identify discrepancies between expected patterns of preservation and what is observed in the archaeological record (O’Shea and Bridges 1989; Roksandic 2002; Larsson 2003; Outram et al., 2005; Stodder 2005; Beckett and Robb 2006; Lieverse et al., 2006; Redfern 2008). Primary inhumations, secondary burials and mass graves all produce different preservational signatures, which can be used to identify the mortuary program pursued by a population. For example, primary burials are likely to preserve more fragile bones and non-persistent articulations (Roksandic 2002), while secondary dispositions where bodies have been moved are more likely to demonstrate incomplete dentition, underrepresentation of normally well-preserved elements and preferential inclusion of specific anatomical regions like crania or limb bones (Olson 1966; Haglund 1997; Roksandic 2002). A full set of taphonomic expectations for different mortuary tracks have been outlined in **Figure 4**. Similarly, data on paleopathology and the age and sex composition of the mortuary population can highlight significant diachronic or synchronic differences in diet, activity patterns, infectious disease prevalence and nutritional stress (Buikstra 1977, Cook and Buikstra 1979; Cook 1981; Goodman 1981; Cohen and Armelagos 1984; Steckel and Rose 2002).

Sex could be estimated for 56% ($n=14$) of adult individuals from N1 while categorical age could be estimated for the entire sample. A preliminary survey of materials from N3 and F1 in summer 2012 suggests that these mortuary locales have a similar degree of preservation to N1, so similar proportions of age and sex estimates should be possible from these areas. Finally, an initial reading of the existing site reports suggests at least 108 individuals were buried in the unstudied mortuary areas (N1, N2, N4, F2, F3). However, this number will definitely increase – the bioarchaeological MNI estimate for N2 more than doubled the number of individuals estimated by the site report, and it is likely that other necropolises will also contain greater numbers of individuals than initially estimated. Importantly, the projected MNI of >100 individuals in the unstudied mortuary areas provides a large enough sample size to confidently ascertain statistical significance.

Domain 2: Grave Goods and Spatial Organization

- Does the number of prestige objects differ between mortuary locales?
- Are there typological differences in the artifacts included in different mortuary structures?
- Does the presence of grave goods co-vary with paleopathology or dietary differences?
- Do differences in burial form or mortuary treatment covary with differences in diet or chronology?

Tomb architecture and grave goods have the potential to reveal both (i) the size of social units being recognized at death (Bloch 1968) and (ii) the number of differentiated social identities being acknowledged in mortuary practice (Binford 1971, O’Shea 1984). For example, the increasing segmentation of megalithic tombs during the late Copper Age in Iberia, and the florescence of individual inhumations under household floors during the Bronze Age, speaks to “an important step away from broadly based communal systems of status and authority, and towards greater individual control of production, prestige and resources” (Mathers 1984: 1173). Similarly, the standardization of grave goods during the second millennium B.C., in tandem with the increase in prestige artifacts at the expense of utilitarian artifacts, suggests an increasing emphasis on smaller units of social

organization than clans or lineages (García Sanuán 2006). Excavations at Marroquíes Bajos have revealed formal variability in tomb type, from primary interments in discrete subterranean structures to collective burials in caves (Espantaleón Jubes 1957, 1960; Serrano Peña et al., 2000), but we do not yet know whether this variability suggests synchronic differentiation or diachronic change. Similarly, there has been no formal analysis of variability in grave goods within and between the mortuary locales at the site. The presence of artifacts like the bronze halberd from N2 (Pérez Martínez 2005) and the famous anthropomorphic ivory idol from Marroquíes Altos (Enríquez Navascués 2000) suggest that prestige objects occur, but are not deposited uniformly throughout the mortuary locales. In order to enhance our understanding of the type of social units being recognized through mortuary practices, and to unpack how such units were distinguished from one another, it is essential to analyze both architectural and artifactual variability at this site.

Domain 3: Stable Isotope Analysis and AMS Radiocarbon Dating

- Does diet differ significantly between and within mortuary locales?
- Are there diachronic changes in diet?
- Do formal characteristics of the mortuary programs reflect change over time?

Previous isotopic studies of diet in archaeological human remains have highlighted the relationship between social stratification and differential access to preferred food types (Ubelaker et al., 2005). In complex societies of the prehistoric American southeast, there is evidence that elites had greater access to meat than non-elites (Peebles and Shoeninger 1981; Ambrose et al., 2003; Yerkes 2005). Zooarchaeological evidence suggests that this pattern may also characterize the Iberian Copper Age (Nocete et al., 2010), but the few dietary isotopic studies that have been conducted to date do not demonstrate significant levels of inter-individual or inter-site dietary differentiation (McClure et al., 2011). While collective mortuary rituals often mask differences among individuals, dietary differentiation is a biological signature that can provide evidence of significantly different lived experiences, despite similar mortuary treatments. Finally, establishing the chronology of the site through radiocarbon dating represents an essential step in determining if and how mortuary practices changed over time and space in the history of Marroquíes Bajos. While human bone collagen has been successfully sampled for dating from Marroquíes Bajos previously, both from individuals from F1 (Sánchez et al. 2005) and human and animal bone from N3 (Cámara et al. 2013), many questions remain unanswered. In particular, the temporal relationship between the mortuary locales, and the use of the mortuary locales relative to the history of the larger site, is unknown. For example, it is currently unclear whether all individuals in the *fosas comunes* were deposited simultaneously, or whether these mortuary locales were used contemporaneously with the necropolises. Similarly, we do not know whether Marroquíes Altos, the sole mortuary locale situated outside the fifth ditch, was established during or after the second half of the third millennium B.C.

The sampling strategy for dietary isotopic analysis entails taking three samples from each discrete structure in the mortuary area (see **Figure 2**) for stable carbon, nitrogen and oxygen isotope analyses. This strategy will provide a sample from each structure in N1, N2 and N4 (15 structures, 45 samples), and three samples each from F2 and F3 (2 structures, 6 samples). These 51 dietary isotopic samples will allow me to examine inter-sexual and inter-age differences within structures, as well as among structures within each necropolis. My AMS radiocarbon sampling strategy is to take two samples from each discrete structure in all unstudied mortuary areas (17 structures, 34 samples). Taking more than one sample per burial is essential for establishing the chronology of their use, as it is possible that some of these collective burials were being reused over broad time spans, as has been documented at other Late Prehistoric sites in Iberia (Lillios et al., 2010; McClure et al., 2011; Cámara et al., 2013;) Overall, this isotopic and radiocarbon sampling strategy maximizes my ability

to explore variability within and among structures, and to determine the amount of variability within and among necropolises and communal graves.

METHODOLOGY

To evaluate the three models outlined in **Table 3**, I have developed a research strategy consisting of four main components: (1) Calculating the Minimum Number of Individuals (MNI) for each structure, and estimating the age and sex of the fragmentary remains when possible; (2) Using the existing site reports at the *Consejería de Cultura de la Junta de Andalucía, (Delegación Provincial de Jaén)* to delineate the stratigraphic context, form and internal structure each mortuary locale; (3) creating an inventory of the grave goods recovered and documented during the salvage excavations, as well as those recovered during bioarchaeological analysis, and (4) Targeting and sampling individuals for dietary isotopic analysis and AMS radiocarbon dating. Guided by the results from my preliminary season of data collection on N1 and N2 (May-August 2013), I will spend five months (May-September) in 2014 continuing to analyze N1 and beginning analysis and sampling of N4 and F2. I will write up my results in September 2014 – August 2015. Funding for the initial season of data collection was obtained from the James Griffin Scholarship Fund; additional funds for the second season will be sought from the Rackham International Research Award, the National Science Foundation, the University of Michigan Rackham Graduate Student Research Grant, and the University of Michigan Museum of Anthropology Radiocarbon Years Before Present Fund. I have obtained permission for analysis of osteological materials from the *Consejería de Cultura y Deporte (Delegación Provincial de Jaén)* and the *Museo de Jaén*.

Domain 1: Bioarchaeological Analysis

The following procedure was used in the analysis of N2 during summer of 2013, but will also be employed in subsequent analyses of N1 and N4. Because human remains from the necropolises had not been processed post-excavation (**Figure 7**), remains were dry-screened to remove sediment prior to data collection. If sediment interfered with element identification, the observation of features, or pathology, bones were gently cleaned using brushes, water and toothpicks. Washed bones were dried in the sun for at least two days before being re-bagged. Teeth and alveolar bone were removed during the initial unpacking of the material, and dry-cleaned separately.

After cleaning, bones were sorted by anatomical region (e.g. foot bones) before element identification (e.g. calcaneus). Fragments that could be identified to the level of element were then compared to larger preserved portions to determine whether conjoins were possible. Working on an element-by-element basis, completion for each bone was recorded according to the zonation method outlined in Knüsel and Outram (2004) and Stodder and Osterholtz (2010). For the long bones, sided individual elements were then compared to determine whether pair-matching was possible (**Figure 8**), to further refine MNI calculation, as outlined in Adams and Konigsberg (2004). Processes of conjoin and refitting are additionally useful as they ensure no individuals will be duplicated when selecting samples for radiocarbon dating and isotopic analysis. Dentition was identified to tooth category, number, arcade and side (e.g. left M³), and all dentition was scored for attrition using the modified Murphy and Scott systems outlined in Buikstra and Ubelaker (2004: 52-3). Grossly observable skeletal or dental pathologies (e.g. enamel hypoplasias, osteoarthritis), were identified using standard reference texts (Ortner 2003), and recorded and scored according to methods outlined in Buikstra and Ubelaker (2004:54-60;108-158). For commingled remains, skeletal and dental MNIs were calculated for the minimum unit of spatial analysis, generally the structural complex the bones were buried in. For remains bagged as individuals (as was the case with N1), both hand-drawn maps from site reports and skeletal inventories were used to establish the MNI.

Taking into account the vagaries of skeletal preservation, age was estimated when possible using a range of techniques, including degree of epiphyseal fusion (Mackay 1961; Scheuer and Black

2004), tooth formation (Thoma and Goldman 1960; Smith 1991) and dental eruption sequences (Buikstra and Ubelaker 2004: 50-51), dental attrition (Brothwell 1991; Gilmore and Grote 2012) the auricular surface of the os coxa (Lovejoy et al., 1984), and the pubic symphyseal face (Brooks and Suchey 1990). Sex was estimated with reference to non-metric cranial traits (Buikstra and Ubelaker 2004: 19-20), the morphology of the pubis (Phenice 1969) and the morphology of the Greater Sciatic Notch (Buikstra and Ubelaker 2004:18).

Domain 2: Grave Goods and Spatial Organization

Archaeological site reports curated by the Junta de Andalucía are not digitized, and are only available in hard copy at the *Consejería de Cultura de Jaén*. Importantly, in the Autonomous Community of Andalucía “rescue excavations do not legally involve in-depth post-excavation analysis of the data obtained” (Costa Caramé et al., 2010: 88). Accordingly, though the rescue excavation of Marroquíes Bajos is documented in regional site reports, much of the resulting material has not been analyzed, and results of the excavations have not been publicly published. During June of 2013 I visited the *Consejería de Cultura* in Jaén, and with the assistance of regional archaeologist Narciso Zafra de la Torre, examined all of the site reports available for the five unanalyzed mortuary locales at Marroquíes (F1, F3, N1, N2 and N4). These site reports contain essential information about the stratigraphic context, internal organization, size and construction of each mortuary locale. While the site reports contained detailed hand drawn maps (**Figure 5**), most were too large to scan, a problem I will resolve by using a portable scanner during my second season of data collection. Digital photographs documenting the excavations of mortuary structures were available for F1 and N2. F2 and N4 have been previously analyzed (Cámara Serrano et al., 2012, 2013; Sánchez et al., 2005), providing comparative information for the other mortuary locales at the site.

All artifacts associated with the Marroquíes Bajos funerary deposits are curated at the Museo de Jaén, where this dissertation research will be conducted. Because of the salvage nature of excavations at the site, artifacts were occasionally accidentally identified as and bagged with human remains (**Figure 6**). For example, cleaning and analysis of the human remains from Structure 45 in Necropolis 2 produced 1.59 kg of ceramic sherds, lithics, shells and a bone awl, in addition to the very unusual “grave goods of complete pottery” described in the site report (Pérez Martínez 2004). In the summer of 2014, I will continue to inventory all artifacts associated with the materials, focusing on the quantity of artifacts and the number of finely-worked or extra-local grave goods (e.g. variscite, ivory, callais, copper) in each burial.

Domain 3: Stable Isotope and AMS Radiocarbon Dating

Finally, in summer 2014, after calculating the MNI for N1, N2 and N4, I will select well-preserved, comparable elements from a sample of the structures in each necropolis to sample for (i) for carbon, nitrogen and oxygen isotope analysis, and (ii) for AMS radiocarbon dating, in order to examine how diet varies relative to space, time, formal aspects of the mortuary structures (e.g. grave goods, type of inhumation) and bioarchaeological characteristics of the individuals interred (e.g. age, sex, anatomical completion). This variation will be tested using statistical resampling methods, that will compare data collected from a single mortuary area to data from the other mortuary areas. This will allow me to test whether differences between mortuary areas are related to sampling error, or are representative of significant formal or bioarchaeological differences between mortuary populations.

QUALIFICATIONS

I am well qualified to undertake this research. I have extensive training in human osteology in archaeological contexts, including a laboratory in human osteology (*ANTHRBIO 477* – University of Michigan), a six-week bioarchaeology and human osteology course (*ASM 583* – Arizona State University, Kampsville), a five-day introduction to the methods of Forensic Anthropology (Maryland

OCME - 25th Annual Forensic Anthropology Course), and a first year medical school Human Gross Anatomy class in (*ANA 7010* - Wayne State University). In addition to my extensive laboratory training, I have spent two field seasons (Summer 2010, Summer 2012) as a field hand on the University of Iowa excavation of the Late Neolithic/ Early Copper Age artificial rockshelter of Bolorés, Portugal. On this project I gained experience in the excavation, recovery and identification of Chalcolithic human remains in an Iberian field context. Furthermore, my work as the Palaeoanthropology Lab Graduate Student Staff Assistant in fall 2012 involved identifying contemporary and historic human remains, as well as formulating a system for cataloguing and organizing these skeletal materials. Finally, I have extensive experience with bioarchaeological approaches to prehistoric social organization: my pre-doctoral research explored the relationship between skeletal indicators of health and a gendered reorganization of economic power in a sample of Middle and Late Woodland remains from the lower Illinois River Valley.

INTELLECTUAL MERIT AND BROADER IMPACTS

The intellectual merit of this project stems from its utility in enhancing our understanding of communal burials, a topic that has merited increasing anthropological attention in recent years (Osterholtz et al., 2013). As Stodder underscores “For those of us accustomed to clearly defined pit features containing extended skeletons with grave goods, the notion of what constitutes a burial and mortuary feature must be reshaped to accommodate the archaeological record in a place where there is in a sense no such thing as a primary burial”(2005: 249). While there has been a florescence of recent research on multi-stage and collective mortuary programs, (Roksandic 2002; Lieverse et al., 2006; Becket and Robb 2006), few Iberian-specific analyses have been conducted that permit us to understand what such sites represent in terms of social organization (Lillios et al., 2010: 35). Importantly, a better understanding of the communal interments so characteristic of the Iberian Chalcolithic will allow for a more detailed understanding of how these amorphously ‘collective’ early complex societies were actually organized.

The broader impacts of this project are two-fold. First, my project involves the analysis of salvage-excavated materials that would otherwise sit untouched in museum storage. The professional expansion of Spanish archaeology during the 1970s (Gilman 1995) and the impressive increase in survey and excavation during the 1980s and 1990s (Díaz-del-Río 2004b; Nocete et al., 2010) has not been matched by an equivalent degree of analysis of recovered cultural materials. The paucity of synthetic work conducted on these types of materials has been bemoaned by Iberianists as an impediment to producing nuanced analyses of Copper Age dynamics (Díaz-del-Río 2004b; Chapman 2008; Costa Caramé et al., 2010; Gilman 2013). This project’s multi-component bioarchaeological and archaeological analysis offers a novel approach to mortuary work in Spain, and should offer a framework for future projects.

Secondly, human remains are a unique type of cultural evidence that merit timely cleaning, analysis, storage and display. Recent guidelines have stressed that researchers must recognize this singularity: “[D]ead people and human remains must not be treated like other objects...the respectful handling of the dead is due on the basis of the concept of human dignity... [human remains of archaeological interest] cannot be excluded from the guarantee of human dignity solely on the basis of their age”(Deterts 2013:44-5). By analyzing unstudied, salvage-excavated collections, my project aids in the development of synthetic models of late prehistory in Iberia, and its bioarchaeological focus ensures that the remains of these Copper Age individuals will be used to make a significant contribution to our understanding of the human past. I will disseminate my results to the academic community in presentations at national and international conferences in multiple fields, publication in peer-reviewed journals, and ultimately a book detailing the ways that the mortuary record of Marroquies Bajos illustrates the development of social complexity in Iberia.

FIGURES

Figure 1: Map of Mortuary Locales at Marroquíes Bajos (courtesy of Narciso Zafra de la Torre)

Figure 2: Number of funerary structures per mortuary locale

Mortuary locale	Number of Structures (Pits or Caves)
N1	6
N2	5
N3	8
N4	4
F1	1
F2	1
F3	1

Figure 3: Archaeological Correlates of Models

Model	Expectations
<p>Model 1: Diachronic change</p> <p>Mortuary variability reflects the shift from the collective ideology of the Copper Age to the more individual focus of the Bronze Age.</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Chronology: Collective burials (N2, F1, F2, F3) will occur earlier in time, while burials emphasizing the individual (N1, N3, N4) will occur later in time; • Grave Goods: Exotic artifacts should be concentrated with more recent mortuary locales, where status differentiation is being represented through grave goods; • Subadults: More elaborate individual child burials in later periods; • Paleopathology: Does not differ significantly between mortuary sites; • Diet: Increased consumption of meat by individuals from N1, N3 and N4, especially in individuals afforded different formal treatments
<p>Model 2: Multi-stage mortuary program</p> <p>Mortuary variability reflects different stages of processing in a multi-stage funerary ritual. Some mortuary locales are areas devoted to primary processing, while others represent secondary burials or ossuaries.</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Chronology: All burial forms will overlap chronologically, suggesting contemporaneous use. • Anatomical Representation: Different locations show different levels of anatomical representation and preservation; • Grave Goods: Primary processing sites have proportionally lower numbers of exotic goods, while secondary sites have higher numbers of exotic goods. • Subadults: Lower representation of subadults at secondary processing sites. • Paleopathology: Higher frequency of paleopathology at primary processing sites, where the majority of the population is interred. • Diet: Greater dietary variability at sites associated with primary processing (more complete, initial inhumations);
<p>Model 3: Social differentiation</p> <p>Mortuary variability is a reflection of different social groups (clans, lineages, sodalities) employing different mortuary programs.</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Chronology: All burial forms will overlap chronologically, suggesting contemporaneous use; • Anatomical Representation: Different mortuary tracks, as revealed through differential mortuary representation, will be associated with different numbers of exotics. • Subadults: Higher status mortuary areas will include higher numbers of subadults; • Paleopathology: Indicators of stress and disease will vary spatially; • Diet: Individuals buried in high-status burial locations will show isotopic evidence of greater consumption of meat.

Figure 4: Taphonomic Indicators of Different Mortuary Tracks

Type of Burial	Taphonomic Indicators
Ossuaries (Diachronous & Synchronous)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • <u>If diachronic</u>: Uniformity in the degree of decomposition (Roksandic 2002). • <u>If synchronic</u>: Variable patterning in anatomical connections, related to differing degrees of decomposition. (Roksandic 2002). • Sorting, elements grouped and spatially segregated from other elements (Olson 1966; Larsson 2003); • Large but fragile bones (e.g. scapulae, pelves) should be well represented (Beckett and Robb, 2006). • Small and fragile bones (e.g. carpals, tarsals) will likely be missing (Beckett and Robb, 2006).
Excarnation by exposure	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Evidence of gnawing, cutmarks and dry bone fractures, weathering or burning (Olson 1966; Redfern 2008) • Archaeological evidence of exposure platforms and/or pits containing disarticulated human remains; • Patterning or differential representation relative to known sequences of disarticulation (e.g. cranium first, legs last) (Redfern 2008).
Primary Burials	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Higher completeness, virtually all bones present (Roksandic, 2002; Beckett and Robb, 2006; Lieveise et al., 2006); • Presence of small bones (Reilly 2003; Beckett and Robb, 2006*); • High articulation – fully or partially articulated individuals present, with both persistent and non-persistent articulations present (Roksandic 2002; Reilly 2003; Lieveise et al., 2006).
Secondary Burials	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Lower completeness and articulation, remains “disorganized” (Olson 1966; Lieveise et al., 2006); • Sorting of human bones, (Olson 1966); • Lower number of small bones observed (e.g. vertebrae, phalanges,) than expected (Olson 1966; Roksandic 2002) • Long bones and ribs heavily outnumbered tabular bones such as pelves and scapulae (Olson 1966). • Weathering or burning may indicate processing or exposure for excarnation (Olson 1966). • Underrepresentation of normally well-preserved elements (Roksandic 2002). • Lower levels of dental completion than expected (teeth susceptible to falling out of the alveoli after the decay of the periodontal ligament) (Roksandic 2002).
Synchronous Primary Burials (Mass Graves)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Partial or full articulation of individuals (Outram et al., 2005). • Evidence of trauma (Outram et al., 2005) • Bioarchaeological signatures of (i) epidemics, (ii) massacres or (iii) ritual suicides of elite households (Roksandic 2002).

* In their simulation of a Neolithic collective burial, Beckett and Robb (2006) found that small bones were underrepresented regardless of burial method (primary or secondary). However, these authors did not control for the potential differential taphonomic preservation of different bones – they in fact note that at the Neolithic site of Poul Nabrone, MNI was calculated with reference to the scaphoid (2006:63). If different carpals and tarsals prove differentially susceptible to preservation (a likely outcome, given their variability in size, form and proportion of cancellous bone), then more targeted predictions need to be made about *which* small bones are likely to survive in the archaeological record.

Figure 5: Photograph of Necropolis 1, Structure 14, Floor 1 Map

Figure 6: Bone awls (right and left) and , ivory bracelet (center). Additional artifacts recovered from bags of human remains, Necropolis 1 (10 cm scale).

Figure 7: Original condition of human remains from Necropolis 2, Structure 44 (foot for scale).

Figure 8: Conjoin and pair-matching of humeri from Necropolis 2, Structure 44, post-cleaning

References Cited

- Adams, B.J. and L.W. Konigsberg
2004 Estimation of the Most Likely Number of Individuals from Commingled Human Skeletal Remains. *American Journal of Physical Anthropology* 125(2):138-51.
- Beckett, J., and J. Robb
2006 Neolithic Burial Taphonomy, Ritual and Interpretation in Britain and Ireland; a Review. In *Social Archaeology of Funerary Remains*, edited by R. Gowland and C.J. Knüsel, pp.57–80. Oxbow Books, Oxford.
- Binford, L.R.
1971 Mortuary Practices: Their Study and Their Potential. *Memoirs of the Society for American Archaeology* 32:6–29.
- Bloch, M.
1968 Tombs and Conservatism Among the Merina of Madagascar. *Man* 3(1):94–104.
- Brooks, S.T. and J.M. Suchey.
1990 Skeletal Age Determination Based on the Os Pubis: A Comparison of the Acsádi-Nemeskéri and Suchey-Brooks Methods. *Human Evolution* 5: 227-238.
- Brothwell, D.R.
1991 *Digging up Bones: The excavation, treatment and study of human skeletal remains*. Third Edition. Oxford University Press, Oxford.
- Brown, J.A.
1971 The Dimensions of Status in the Burials at Spiro. *Memoirs of the Society for American Archaeology*: 92–112.
- 1981 The Search for Rank in Prehistoric Burials. In *The Archaeology of Death*, edited by R. Chapman, I. Kinnes, and K. Randsborg, pp.25-37. Cambridge University Press, Cambridge.
- 1995 On Mortuary Analysis - with Special Reference to the Saxe-Binford Research Program. In *Regional Approaches to Mortuary Analysis*, edited by L. Anderson Beck, pp. 3–26, Plenum Press, New York.
- Buikstra, J. E.
1977 Biocultural Dimensions of Archeological Study: A Regional Perspective. In *Biocultural Adaptation in Prehistoric America*, 11:67–84.
- Buikstra, J. E. and D.J. Ubelaker
1994 Standards for Data Collection from Human Skeletal Remains, Edited by J.E. Buikstra and D.J. Ubelaker. Arkansas Archaeological Survey Research Series No.44, Fayetteville.

Cámara Serrano, J. A., L. Spanedda, R. Sánchez Susí, M.F. García Cuevas, A. González Herrera, and J. Nicás Perales

2012 La cronología absoluta de Marroquíes (Jaén) en el contexto de la Prehistoria Reciente del Alto Guadalquivir. *ANTIQUITAS* 24: 81–94.

Cámara Serrano, J. A., R. Sánchez Susí, Z. Laffranchi, S. Martín Flórez, J.A. Riquelme Cantal, L. Spanedda, M.F. García Cuevas, A. González Herrera, S. A. Jiménez Brobeil, and J. Nicás Perales

2013 La Cronología y variedad de los sistemas funerarios en Marroquíes. Una aproximación desde las excavaciones del Sistema Tranviario de Jaén.” *SAGVNTVM. Papeles Del Laboratorio de Arqueología de Valencia* 44: 47–66.

Cannon, A.

1989 Historical Dimension in Mortuary Expressions of Status and Sentiment. *Current Anthropology* 30(4): 437-458.

Chapman, R.W.

1977 Burial Practices – An Area of Mutual Interest. *Archaeology and Anthropology: Areas of Mutual Interest. BAR Supplementary Series* 19: 19-33.

1978 The evidence for prehistoric water control in southeast Spain. *Journal of Arid Environments* 1:261-274.

1981 Archaeological Theory and Communal Burial in Prehistoric Europe. In *Pattern of the Past: Studies in Honour of David Clarke*, pp.387–411, Cambridge University Press: New York.

1990 *Emerging complexity: The later prehistory of south-east Spain, Iberia and the west Mediterranean*. Cambridge University Press, Cambridge.

1995 Ten Years After – Megaliths, Mortuary Practices, and the Territorial Model. In *Regional Approaches to Mortuary Analysis*. edited by Lane A. Beck, pp. 29-51. Plenum Press, New York.

2003 *Archaeologies of Complexity*. Routledge, New York.

2008 Producing Inequalities: Regional Sequences in Later Prehistoric Southern Spain. *Journal of World Prehistory* 21(3-4):195-260.

Childe, V.G.

1945 Directional Changes in Funerary Practices During 50,000 Years. *Man* 45 (3-4): 13-19.

Cohen, M.N., and G.J. Armelagos (editors)

1984 *Paleopathology at the Origins of Agriculture*, Academic Press, Orlando.

- Cohen, M.N. and G.M.M. Crane-Kramer (editors)
 2007 *Ancient health: skeletal indicators of agricultural and economic intensification*.
 University Press of Florida, Gainesville
- Cook, D.C.
 1981. Mortality, Age-Structure and Status in the Interpretation of Stress Indicators in Prehistoric Skeletons: a Dental Example from the Lower Illinois Valley. In *The Archaeology of Death*, edited by R. Chapman, I. Kinnes, and K. Randsborg, pp. 133-144. Cambridge University Press, Cambridge.
- Cook, D.C., and J.E. Buikstra.
 1979. Health and Differential Survival in Prehistoric Populations: Prenatal Dental Defects. *American Journal of Physical Anthropology* 51(4): 649–64.
- Costa Caramé, M.E., M. Díaz-Zorita Bonilla, L. García Sanjuán and D.W. Wheatley.
 2010 The Copper Age Settlement of Valencina de la Concepción (Seville, Spain): Demography, Metallurgy and Spatial Organization. *Trabajos de Prehistoria* 67(1): 85-98.
- Crespo Kayser, A.L, C. Alhambra Galloway, C. Espinar Kayser, T. Pérez Vallejo, R. Lisalde Martínez, and M. Gorbea Pérez
 2009 *Memoria final de la intervención arqueológica preventiva en el solar situado en la parcela D-PAD (Antiguo T3) del SUNP 1. Zona Arqueológica de Marroquíes Bajos (Jaén)*. (Expediente 173/07)
- Cruz Berrocal, M., L. García Sanjuán and A. Gilman (editors)
 2013 *The prehistory of Iberia: debating early social stratification and the state*.
 Routledge, New York.
- Delibes de Castro, G., J.I. Herrán Martínez, J. de Santiago Pardo and J. del Val Recio.
 1995 Evidence for Social Complexity in the Copper Age of the Northern Meseta. In *The Origins of Complex Societies in Late Prehistoric Iberia*, edited by K. Lillios, pp.44-63, International Monographs in Prehistory, Ann Arbor.
- Deterts, D. (editor)
 2013 *Recommendations for the Care of Human Remains in Museums and Collections*.
 Translated by A. Wesche. Deutscher Museumsbund.
- Díaz-Andreu, M.
 1995 Complex Societies in Copper and Bronze Age Iberia: A Reappraisal. *Oxford Journal of Archaeology* 14(1): 23-39.
- Díaz-del-Río, P.
 2004a Copper Age Ditched Enclosures in Central Iberia. *Oxford Journal of Archaeology* 23(2): 107-121.

2004b Factionalism and Collective Labor in Copper Age Iberia. *Trabajos de Prehistoria* 61(2): 85–98.

2006 An Appraisal of Social Inequalities in Central Iberia (c. 5300-1600 CAL BC). In *Social Inequality in Iberian Late Prehistory* edited by P. Díaz-del-Río and L. García Sanjuán, pp.67–76. Archaeopress, Oxford.

2013 Las agregaciones de población del III Milenio AC en la Península Ibérica. In *El asentamiento prehistórico de Valencina de La Concepción (Sevilla): investigación y tutela en el 150 aniversario del descubrimiento de La Pastora*. Edited by L. García Sanjuán, J.M. Vargas Jiménez, V. Hurtado Pérez, T. Ruiz Moreno, and R. Cruz-Auñón Briones, pp. 65-76. University of Seville, Seville.

Díaz-del-Río, P. and L.García Sanjuán.

2006 *Social Inequality in Iberian Late Prehistory*. Archaeopress, Oxford.

Enríquez Navascués, J.J.

2000 Nuevos ídolos antropomorfos calcolíticos de la cuenca media del Guadiana. *SPAL: Revista de prehistoria y arqueología de la Universidad de Sevilla* 9: 351-368.

Espantaleón, R.

1957 La Nécropolis Eneolítica de <Marroquíes Altos>. *Boletín del Instituto de Estudios Giennenses* 13: 165–174.

Espantaleón, R.

1960 La necrópolis en cueva artificial de Marroquíes Altos, *Boletín del Instituto de Estudios Giennenses*, 26: 35-50.

Forenbaier, S.

1999 *Production and Exchange of Bifacial Flaked Stone Artifacts During the Portuguese Chalcolithic*. Archaeopress, Oxford.

García Cuevas, M. F.

2005 Intervención arqueológica en Carretera de Madrid esquina RU-16. (Expediente 5/05).

García Cuevas, M. F., J. Nicás Perales, A. González Herrera, and R. Sánchez Susí

2012 Memoria preliminar relativa a la AAP, excavación arqueológica, en el sistema tranviario de Jaén. (Tramo 3 - Vivero de empresas). (Expediente 84/09).

García Sanjuán, L.

2006 Funerary Ideology and Social Inequality in the Late Prehistory of the Iberian South-West (c. 3300-850 Cal BC). In *Social Inequality in Iberian Late Prehistory*

- edited by P. Díaz-del-Río and L. García Sanjuán, pp.149–169. Archaeopress, Oxford.
- García Sanjuán, L. and P. Díaz-del-Río.
 2006 Advances, Problems and Perspectives in the Study of Social Inequality in Iberian Late Prehistory. In *Social Inequality in Iberian Late Prehistory*, edited by P. Díaz-del-Río and L. García Sanjuán, pp.1–9. Archaeopress, Oxford.
- García Sanjuán, L., M. Lucíañez Triviño, T. Schumacher and D. Wheatley
 2013 Ivory craftsmanship, trade and social significance in the southern Iberian Copper Age: the evidence from the PP4-Montelirio sector of Valencina de la Concepción (Seville, Spain). *European Journal of Archaeology* 16(4): 610-635.
- García Sanjuán, L. and M. Murillo-Barroso
 2013 Social Complexity in Copper Age Southern Iberia (c. 3200-2200 Cal BC): Reviewing the ‘State’ Hypothesis at Valencina de La Concepción (Seville, Spain). In *The Prehistory of Iberia: Debating Early Social Stratification and the State*, edited by M. Cruz Berrocal, L. García Sanjuán and A. Gilman, pp.181–217, Routledge, New York
- Gilman, A.
 1987 Unequal Development in Copper Age Iberia. In *Specialization, Exchange and Complex Societies*, edited by E.M. Brumfiel and T.K. Earle. pp. 22-29, *New Directions in Archaeology*, Cambridge University Press, Cambridge.
- 1995 Recent Trends in the Archaeology of Spain. In *The Origins of Complex Societies in Late Prehistoric Iberia*, edited by K. Lillios, pp.1-6, *International Monographs in Prehistory*, Ann Arbor.
- 2001 Assessing Political Development in Copper and Bronze Age Southeast Spain. In *From Leaders to Rulers*, edited by J. Haas, pp.59–81. Kluwer Academic/Plenum Publishers, New York.
- 2013 Were There States during the Later Prehistory of Southern Iberia? In *The Prehistory of Iberia: Debating Early Social Stratification and the State*, edited by M. Cruz Berrocal, L. García Sanjuán and A. Gilman, pp.10-28, Routledge, New York.
- Gilman, A. and J.B. Thornes
 1985 *Land use and prehistory in south-east Spain*. Allen and Unwin. London.
- Gilmore, C.C. and M. N. Grote.
 2012 Estimating Age from Adult Occlusal Wear: A Modification of the Miles Method. *Journal of Physical Anthropology* 149:181-192.

Goldstein, L.

1981. One-dimensional Archaeology and Multi-dimensional People: Spatial Organisation and Mortuary Analysis. In *The Archaeology of Death*, edited by R. Chapman, I. Kinnes, and K. Randsborg, pp. 53–69. Cambridge University Press, Cambridge.

Goodenough, W.H.

1965. Rethinking ‘Status’ and ‘Role’ – Toward a General Model of the Cultural Organization of Social Relationships. In *The Relevance of models for Social Anthropology*, edited by Michael Banton, pp. 1-24. A.S.A. Monographs, No. 1. Tavistock Publications, London.

Haglund, W.D.

- 1997 Scattered Skeletal Human Remains: Search Strategy Considerations for Locating Missing Teeth. In *Forensic Taphonomy: The Postmortem Fate of Human Remains*, edited by W.D. Haglund and M.H.Sorg, pp.383-394. CRC Press, Boca Raton.

Harrison, R.

- 1985 The “Policultivo Ganadero”, or the Secondary Products Revolution in Spanish Agriculture, 5000-1000 bc. *Proceedings of the Prehistoric Society* 51:75-102

Hijiya, J.A.

- 1983 American Gravestones and Attitudes Toward Death: A Brief History. *Proceedings of the American Philosophical Society* 127(5): 339-363.

Knüsel, C.J. and A.K. Outram

- 2004 Fragmentation: The Zonation Method Applied to Fragmented Human Remains from Archaeological Contexts. *Environmental Archaeology* 9:85-97.

Kroeber, A.L.

- 1927 Disposal of the Dead. *American Anthropologist* 29(3): 308-315.

Larsson, Asa M.

- 2003 Secondary Burial Practices in the Middle Neolithic Causes and Consequences. *Current Swedish Archaeology* 11: 153–170.

Lieverse, A.R., A.W. Weber, and O.I. Goriunova.

- 2006 Human Taphonomy at Khuzhir-Nuge XIV, Siberia: a New Method for Documenting Skeletal Condition.” *Journal of Archaeological Science* 33 (8): 1141–1151.

Lillios, K.T.

- 1995 *The Origins of Complex Societies in Late Prehistoric Iberia*. International Monographs in Prehistory, Ann Arbor.

1999 Objects of Memory: The Ethnography and Archaeology of Heirlooms. *Journal of Archaeological Method and Theory* 6 (3): 235–262.

Lillios, K.T., A.J Waterman, and J.A. Artz.

2010 The Neolithic-Early Bronze Age Mortuary Rockshelter of Bolores , Torres Vedras , Portugal. *Journal of Field Archaeology* 35 (1): 19–39.

Lovejoy, C.O., R.S. Meindl, T.R. Pryzbeck, and R.P. Mensforth.

1985 Chronological Metamorphosis of the Auricular Surface of the Ilium: A New Method for the Determination of Adult Skeletal Age at Death. *American Journal of Physical Anthropology* 68: 15-28.

Lucas de Pellicer, M.R.

1968 Otra cueva artificial en la necropolis <Marroquies Altos> de Jaén, (Cueva IV). *Excavaciones arqueológicas en España* 62: 3-29.

Lull, V.

2000 Argaric society: death at home. *Antiquity* 74:581-590.

Lull, V., R.Micó, C. Rihuete and R. Risch

2005 Property relations in the bronze age of South-western Europe: An archaeological analysis of infant burials from El Argar (Almeria, Spain). *Proceedings of the Prehistoric Society* 71: 247-268.

Mackay, R. H.

1961 *Skeletal maturation (chart)*. Eastman Kodak, Rochester.

Manzano Castillo, A. and J.L. Martínez Ocaña.

2005 *Informe de la Intervención arqueológica en C/ Cristo Rey N°5, de Jaén en Cuevas Artificiales de Marroquies Altos*. Expediente 56/05. Guiomar H.C.M.

Mathers, C.

1984a Beyond the Grave: The Context and Wider Implications of Mortuary Practice in South-Eastern Spain. In *Papers in Iberian Archaeology*, edited by T.F. Blagg, R.F. Jones, and S. Keay, pp.13–46, BAR, Oxford.

Mathers, C.

1984b Linear Regression', Inflation and Prestige Competition – Second Millennium Transformations in Southeast Spain. In *Early Settlement in the Western Mediterranean Islands and Their Peripheral Areas: The Deya Conference of Prehistory*, edited by W. Waldren, R.W. Chapman, J. Lewthwaite, and R.C. Kennard, pp.1167–1196, BAR International Series, Oxford.

McClure, S.B, O. García, C. Roca de Togores, B. Culleton, and D. Kennett.

- 2011 Osteological and Paleodietary Investigation of Burials from Cova de La Pastora, Alicante, Spain. *Journal of Archaeological Science* 38 (2): 420–428.
- Metcalf, P.
1981 Meaning and Materialism: The Ritual Economy of Death. *Man* 16 (4): 563–578.
- Micó Pérez, R.
1995 Los Millares and the Copper Age of the Iberian Southeast. In *The Origins of Complex Societies in Late Prehistoric Iberia*, edited by K. Lillios, pp.169-176, International Monographs in Prehistory, Ann Arbor.
- Molina, F. and J.A. Cámara
2005 Guía del yacimiento arqueológico Los Millares. Dirección General de Bienes Culturales. Consejería de Cultura de la Junta de Andalucía.
- Nocete, F.
2006 The First Specialized Copper Industry in the Iberia Peninsula: Cabezo Juré (2900-2200 BC). *Antiquity* 80 (309): 62-81.
- Nocete, F., R. Sáez, J.M. Nieto, R. Cruz-Auñón, R. Cabrero, E. Alex and M.R. Bayona.
2005 Circulation of silicified oolitic limestone blades in South-Iberia (Spain and Portugal) during the third millennium B.C.: an expression of a core/Periphery framework. *Journal of Anthropological Archaeology* 24 (1): 62–81
- Nocete, F. G. Queipo, R. Sáez, J.M. Nieto, N. Inácio, M.R. Bayona, A. Peramo, J.M. Vargas, R. Cruz-Auñón, J.I. Gil-Ibarguchi and J.F.Santos.
2008 The smelting quarter of Valencina de la Concepción (Seville, Spain): the specialized copper industry in a political centre of the Guadalquivir Valley during the Third millennium BC (2750-2500 BC). *Journal of Archaeological Science* 35(3): 717-732.
- Nocete, F., R.Lizcano, A. Peramo, and E. Gómez.
2010 Emergence, Collapse and Continuity of the First Political System in the Guadalquivir Basin from the Fourth to the Second Millennium BC: The Long-term Sequence of Úbeda (Spain). *Journal of Anthropological Archaeology* 29(2): 219–237.
- Olson, Alan P.
1966 A Mass Secondary Burial from Northern Arizona. *American Antiquity* 31 (6): 822–826.
- Ortner, D.J.

2003 *Identification of Pathological Conditions in Human Skeletal Remains*. 2nd Edition. Academic Press, Amsterdam.

O'Shea, J.M.

1984 *Mortuary Variability: An Archaeological Investigation*. Academic Press, Orlando.

O'Shea, J.M., and P.S. Bridges.

1989 The Sargent Site Ossuary (25CU28) Custer County, Nebraska. *Plains Anthropologist* 34(123):7-21.

Osterholtz, A.J., K.M Baustian and D.L. Martin.

2013 *Commingled and Disarticulated Human Remains: Working Toward Improved Theory, Method and Data*. Springer, New York.

Outram, A.K., C.J. Knüsel, S. Knight, and A. F. Harding.

2005 Understanding Complex Fragmented Assemblages of Human and Animal Remains: a Fully Integrated Approach. *Journal of Archaeological Science* 32 (12): 1699–1710.

Palgi, P. and H. Abramovitch

1984. Death: A Cross-Cultural Perspective. *Annual Review of Anthropology* 13:385-417.

Parker Pearson, M.

1982. Mortuary Practices, Society and Ideology: An Ethnoarchaeological Study. In *Symbolic and Structural Archaeology*, edited by I. Hodder, pp. 99-113. Cambridge University Press, Cambridge.

2009 *The Archaeology of Death and Burial*. The History Press, Stroud.

Peebles, C.S., and S.M. Kus.

1977. Some Archaeological Correlates of Ranked Societies. *American Antiquity* 42 (3): 421–448.

Peebles, C.S., and M.J. Schoeninger.

1981 Notes on the Relationship Between Social Status and Diet at Moundville. *Southeastern Archaeological Conference Bulletin* 24: 96–97.

Pérez Martínez, M.D.C.

2005 Memoria Final de la Intervención Arqueológica Preventiva en Bulevar II Fase. Sector SUNP 1. Excmo Ayuntamiento de Jaén, Jaén.

Phenice, T.

1969 A Newly Developed Visual Method of Sexing in the Os Pubis. *American Journal of Physical Anthropology* 30:297-301.

Rainville, L.

1999 Hanover Deathscapes: Mortuary Variability in New Hampshire, 1770-1920. *Ethnohistory* 46(3): 541–597.

Redfern, R.

2008 New Evidence for Iron Age Secondary Burial Practice and Bone Modification from Gussage All Saints and Maiden Castle (Dorset, England). *Oxford Journal of Archaeology* 27 (3): 281–301.

Renfrew, C.

1973 Monuments, Mobilization and Social Organization in Neolithic Wessex. In *The Explanation of Culture Change: Models in Prehistory*, edited by C. Renfrew, pp. 539-59. Gerald Duckworth & Co., Gloucester, UK.

Roksandic, M.

2002 Position of Skeletal Remains as a Key to Understanding Mortuary Behavior. In *Advances in Forensic Taphonomy*, edited by W.D. Haglund and M.H. Sorg, pp.100–113. CRC Press, Boca Raton.

Sánchez, A., J.P. Bellón and C. Rueda

2005 New Data About the Archaeological Area of Marroquíes Bajos: The Fifth Ditch. *Trabajos de Prehistoria* 62 (2): 151–164.

Saxe, A.

1970. *Social Dimensions of Mortuary Practices*. Unpublished Ph.D. dissertation, University of Michigan, Ann Arbor.

Scheuer, L. and S. Black.

2004 *The Juvenile Skeleton*. Elsevier, London.

Schumacher, T.X.

2012 *Chalkolithische und Frühbronzezeitliche Elfenbeinobjekte auf der Iberischen Halbinsel. Studien zu Herkunft, Austasch, Verarbeitung und sozialer Bedeutung von Elfenbein*. Iberia Archaeologica 16, Fasc. 2. Verlag Phillip von Zabern. Darmstadt/Mainz,

Serrano Peña, J.E, J. Cano Carrillo, Y. Jimenez Morillas, and F. Alcala Lirio.

2000 *Urbanizacion SUNP-1 (1ª Fase) de Jaén. Intervención arqueológica de urgencia informe de los tramos afectados en: distribuidor Sur, Calle A y Calle 1*. EPSA, Jaén.

Sherratt, A.

1983 The Secondary Exploitation of Animals in the Old World. *World Archaeology* 15 (1): 90–104.

Smith, B.H.

1991 Standards of human tooth formation and dental age assessment. In *Advances in Dental Anthropology*, edited by M. Kelley and C.S. Larsen, pp.143-168, Alan R. Liss, New York.

Steckel, R.H. and J.C. Rose (editors)

2002. *The backbone of history: health and nutrition in the Western Hemisphere*. Cambridge, Cambridge University Press.

Stodder, A.L.W.

2005 The Bioarchaeology and Taphonomy of Mortuary Ritual on the Sepik Coast, Papua New Guinea.” In *Interacting with the Dead; Perspectives on Mortuary Archaeology for the New Millennium*, edited by G.F.M. Rakita, J.E. Buikstra, L. Anderson Beck, and S.R. Williams, pp.228–50.University Press of Florida, Gainesville.

Stodder, A.L.W. and A. J. Osterholtz

2010 Analysis of the processed human remains from the Sacred Ridge Site: Methods and Data Collection Protocol. In *Animas-La Plata Project*, edited by J.M. Potter, T.D. Yoder, A.L. Wesson, E.M. Perry and J.P.Chuipka, pp. 243-278. SWCA anthropological research paper, no.10, Phoenix.

Tainter, J.A.

1975 Social inference and mortuary practices: an experiment in numerical classification. *World Archaeology* 7, pp. 1-15.

1978 Mortuary Practices and the Study of Prehistoric Social Systems. In *Advances in Archaeological Method and Theory*, edited by M.Schiffer, pp.105-141. Academic Press, New York.

Thoma, K.H. and H.M. Goldman

1960 *Oral Pathology*. Fifth Edition. Mosby, St. Louis.

Ubelaker, D.H., M.A. Katzenberg, and L.G. Doyon.

1995 Status and diet in precontact highland Ecuador. *American Journal of Physical Anthropology* 97(4):403-11

Ucko, P.J.

1969 Ethnography and Archaeological Interpretation of Funerary Remains. *World Archaeology* 262-280.

Vicent García, J.M.

1995 Early Social Complexity in Iberia: Some Theoretical Remarks. In *The Origins of Complex Societies in Late Prehistoric Iberia*, edited by K. Lillios, pp.177-183, International Monographs in Prehistory, Ann Arbor.

Waterman, A.J., and J.T Thomas.

2011 “When the Bough Breaks: Childhood Mortality and Burial Practice in Late Neolithic Atlantic Europe.” *Oxford Journal of Archaeology* 30 (2): 165–183.

Whitley, J.

2002 Too Many Ancestors. *Antiquity* 76: 119–126.

Yerkes, R.W.

2005 Bone Chemistry, Body Parts, and Growth Marks: Evaluating Ohio Hopewell and Cahokia Mississippian Seasonality, Subsistence, Ritual and Feasting. *American Antiquity* 70(2):241-265.

Zafra de la Torre, N., F. Hornos Mata and M. Castro López.

1999 Una macro-aldea en el origen del modo de vida campesino: Marroquíes Bajos (Jaén) c. 2500-2000 cal. ANE. *Trabajos de Prehistoria* 56(1): 77-102.

Zafra de la Torre, N. and F. Hornos Mata.

2003 Sucesión y simultaneidad en un gran asentamiento: La cronología de la macro-aldea de Marroquíes Bajos, Jaén. c. 2500-2000 cal. ANE. *Trabajos de Prehistoria* 60(1): 79-90.

FACILITIES, EQUIPMENT & OTHER RESOURCES

FACILITIES: Identify the facilities to be used at each performance site listed and, as appropriate, indicate their capacities, pertinent capabilities, relative proximity, and extent of availability to the project. Use "Other" to describe the facilities at any other performance sites listed and at sites for field studies. USE additional pages as necessary.

Laboratory: All data collection will be conducted at the Museum of Jaén in Jaén, Spain.

Clinical:

Animal:

Computer: A tablet will be used when collecting and entering data.

Office:

Other:

MAJOR EQUIPMENT: List the most important items available for this project and, as appropriate identifying the location and pertinent capabilities of each.

OTHER RESOURCES: Provide any information describing the other resources available for the project. Identify support services such as consultant, secretarial, machine shop, and electronics shop, and the extent to which they will be available for the project. Include an explanation of any consortium/contractual arrangements with other organizations.

Data Management Plan

The results of this research will be used to write a doctoral dissertation at the University of Michigan. All of the data collection will take place in Spain, and all materials analyzed in this project will continue to be curated at the Museum of Jaén in Jaén, Spain. The sole exception to this is the samples collected for AMS radiocarbon dating and dietary isotopic analysis, the analysis of which will be conducted in the U.S. A necessary component of this project involves cleaning skeletal material in order to analyze it, which will help in preserving and protecting the material so that future researchers can also examine it.

I will facilitate access to data collected by the project in several ways. First, the inventory of material culture and bioarchaeological specimens will be shared with the Museum of Jaén, as will the digitized site reports from the Regional Ministry of Culture. I began this process in Summer 2013 by sharing a detailed synopsis of the data I had collected that season with Francisca Hornos Mata, museum director at the Museum of Jaén. Second, all of the raw data from spreadsheets and detailed data tables from my bioarchaeological analyses will be provided as appendices to my dissertation. International researchers can access my dissertation through the ProQuest system, which provides digital copies of all University of Michigan dissertations. In Spain, I will personally provide copies of my dissertation and all publications deriving from the project to the Museum of Jaén and the Regional Ministry of Culture in Jaén. Finally, I will personally create a bioarchaeology database so that interested parties may access the skeletal information from this project, to use in comparative research in Iberia or elsewhere. I will create a link to the bioarchaeology database on my personal University of Michigan Anthropology Department webpage.